

significantly (see table). Chalkiness scores, protein content, and gel consistency tests also were significantly different. But gel consistency values can

be taken as similar because they ranged from 41 to 60 mm.

Cooked grain length of DM16-5-1 was less than that of Basmati 370; in

FG6, it was the same as in IR6. Aroma was strong in Basmati 370 and moderately strong in DM16-5-1. IR6 and FG6 had no aroma. □

Grain quality characteristics of some rice varieties

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We evaluated 36 lines and varieties for yield and grain quality characteristics. Plot size was 3.6 × 2 m with 20- × 20-cm plant spacing.

Afaa Mwanza and M38 had the highest grain yields, followed by IR46,

IR36, M40, IR42, and 1ET2379; CR1005 and IR5 had the lowest (see table).

The materials tested differed significantly in grain length to breadth ratio: the highest ratio was for Faya Theresa (slender), and the lowest ratio for F46 (medium). Supa India had the longest grains (extra long) and Cross 10 the shortest (medium).

Amylose content varied, 19-28%. Popular varieties in Tanzania — Afaa Mwanza, Faya Theresa, Supa India,

and Kihogo Red — had intermediate amyloses, as do a number of the introduced varieties.

It was not possible to separate high-amylose rices into those with soft and hard gel consistency because laboratory facilities are limited. □

Grain yield and quality characteristics of some rice varieties. Ngerengere, Tanzania.

Line or variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain length (mm)	Size category	Length: breadth	Shape	Amylose content (%)	Type
M38	7.2	7.4	Long	4.5	Slender	21	Intermediate
Afaa Mwanza	7.1	6.7	Long	3.4	Slender	24	Intermediate
M40	6.9	7.0	Long	3.5	Slender	2.4	Intermediate
IR46	6.8	6.6	Long	3.4	Slender	22	Intermediate
IR36	6.6	5.9	Medium	3.4	Slender	28	High
IR42	6.5	6.8	Long	2.7	Medium	23	Intermediate
IR48	6.3	6.3	Medium	3.0	Slender	23	Intermediate
IET2379	6.3	6.4	Medium	3.3	Slender	28	High
TOX502-25-115	6.1	7.4	Long	3.2	Slender	20	Low
IR34	6.0	7.1	Long	4.4	Slender	25	High
Cross 14	6.0	6.01	Medium	2.6	Medium	21	Intermediate
M26	6.0	6.5	Medium	2.7	Medium	23	Intermediate
Faya Theresa	5.9	6.5	Medium	4.7	Slender	22	Intermediate
Cross 3	5.7	6.01	Medium	3.4	Slender	22	Intermediate
F19	5.6	5.8	Medium	3.3	Slender	22	Intermediate
TOX494-5-1-B-2	5.6	7.5	Long	4.1	Slender	22	Intermediate
M48	5.4	6.7	Long	3.8	Slender	19	Low
Cross 10	5.3	5.7	Medium	3.1	Slender	24	Intermediate
Supa India	5.3	7.7	Extra long	3.6	Slender	23	Intermediate
Kihogo Red	5.1	7.1	Long	3.6	Slender	24	Intermediate
IR3274-348-1-6	5.1	5.7	Medium	2.8	Medium	25	High
M9	4.9	6.6	Long	3.7	Slender	28	High
B57C-MD-10-2	4.9	6.5	Medium	3.3	Slender	25	High
Cross	74.8	5.9	Medium	2.7	Medium	21	Intermediate
IR4570-124-3	4.8	6.6	Long	3.7	Slender	21	Intermediate
F46	4.8	6.5	Long	2.6	Medium	25	High
M50	4.5	6.8	Long	4.2	Slender	26	High
BKN6986-147-6	4.4	7.1	Long	3.0	Slender	26	High
IITA63-84	4.4	7.4	Long	3.2	Slender	24	Intermediate
IR5931-81-1-1	4.2	6.7	Long	3.6	Slender	28	High
M13	4.1	6.7	Long	3.5	Slender	20	Low
Kinandang Patong	3.5	7.30	Long	3.6	Slender	23	Intermediate
IR1539-823-1-4	3.5	6.69	Long	3.6	Slender	26	High
Ram Tulasi	3.2	6.70	Long	3.2	Slender	24	Intermediate
CR1005	2.0	6.61	Long	3.5	Slender	22	Intermediate
IR5	2.1	6.46	Medium	3.4	Slender	23	Intermediate
Mean	5.2	6.65		3.4		23	
CV (%)	19.4	5.99		7.7			

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Physicochemical properties of discolored rice grains

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Discolored grains of ITA307 were obtained from IITA's high rainfall station at Onne in southern Nigeria. The samples were divided into healthy (glume discoloration 1-5%) and discolored (more than 5% discolored) grains.

Part of each sample was parboiled in the laboratory. (Parboiled rice is widely accepted in Nigeria and other West African countries.)

Discolored grains had lower dry weights for rough and brown rice than healthy grains. Head rice yield is also low (see table).

After parboiling, milling yields, translucency, and hardness improved for both healthy and discolored grains. Discolored glumes did not necessarily result in discolored milled rice. However, parboiling accentuated discoloration.

In ITA307, cooking time and gelatinization temperature were not much affected by discoloration. Amylose content slightly decreased in discolored grains. □